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CADRE Work Package 2

Analysis of the required functions of CADRE Services

Work Package 2

There are five Work Packages (WPs) that enable project partners to translate the Five Safes model and develop policy and technical requirements that inform platform development. Of the three phases of the project (Conceptualisation, Development, Operations), in phase #1 'Conceptualisation' the WP1 focused on the development of the conceptual framework whereas WP2 concentrates on the information exchange protocols (aka "the protocols"). In this report, we describe the pathway to the information exchange of CADRE services using persistent identifiers (PID)¹. There are two main use cases for the information exchange in/across this domain; the first use case being interlinking of research objects, and the second application is metadata enrichment. The following sections describe the details of these use cases, related components, and potential integration with CADRE partners' systems and international PID providers.

Metadata Interlinking and Metadata Enrichment

To ensure connectivity and transparency in research, it is recommended to implement procedures, automated and semi-automated functions and rules that enable us to connect our research objects across the entire CADRE ecosystem. Such connected environments ensure interlinking and enrichment of the metadata used.

Metadata interlinking can be defined as the linking of research objects in the closed CADRE ecosystem. Metadata interlinking enables the identification of data accessed by researchers throughout the CADRE ecosystem and other platforms such as ORCID, DataCite and Research Data Australia.

- Identifying data used by researchers across other platforms
 - dataset {source: ADA, AURIN} linked to
 - research activity {source: Data CO-OP}
- Identifying researchers accessing data across CADRE ecosystem
 - researcher {source: ORCID}
 - linked to (or request access to) dataset 1 {source: ADA},

¹ <https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/articles/360006971013>

- linked to (or request access to) dataset 2 {source: AURIN},
 - linked to (or request access to) dataset 3 {source: Data CO-OP}, or
 - participate in a research activity {source: Data CO-OP}
- Metadata Enrichment can be defined as the linking of research objects using PIDs across the global open scholarly networks (Table 1).

Table 1. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) connections across the global network of scholarly works

PID connections	Description
Data → ORCID	Connecting publications and datasets to researchers
ORCID → Data.DOI	Connecting researchers to datasets
Data → Publication → DOI ISBN	Data citation in publications and books
Data → Organisation → FundRef	Connecting datasets to funding organisations using FundRef DOI
Data → Organisation → ROR	Connecting datasets to organisations using ROR open identifier
Data → Organisation → WikiData	Connecting datasets to organisations using WikiData ID
Data → Grant → DOI	Connecting datasets to grants using CrossRef grant identifiers

Persistent Identifier Adoption by Project Partners

As part of the Five Safes model, it is essential to deem the people involved in a project are safe, therefore, CADRE project partners adopt PIDs to help identify whether the persons participating in the project are safe people.

PIDs are distinguishing identifiers that are unique to each researcher and organisation. PIDs are identifiers that ensure persistent, unique and interoperable management of content across digital networks in an automated and organised manner².

Table 2 shows the current state of integrating PIDs into CADRE ecosystem. For example, DOI is adopted by the following partners, ADA, Data CO-OP and AURIN, to identify and link specific datasets.

² Paskin, N. (2010). Digital object identifier (DOI®) system. Encyclopedia of library and information sciences, 3, 1586-1592.

Table 2. Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) adopted by CADRE project partners.

Researcher	Dataset	Grant	Publication	Organisation		
ORCID	DOI	DOI**	DOI	ROR	WikiData	GRID
<i>Project Partners</i>						
ADA	ADA	-	ADA	Data CO-OP***		
Data CO-OP	Data CO-OP	-	Data CO-OP			
	AURIN*	-				

* Only some records.

** No adoption of DOI or other PIDs; however, both ADA and Data CO-OP capture grant numbers. This can potentially lead to the early adoption of new CrossRef DOIs for Australian Research Council (ARC) grants.

*** No active adoption of ROR, WikiData, GRID; however, Data CO-OP has experimented with WikiData ID.

Requirements for Interlinking Services

1. Ability to obtain information about researchers who need access to data
2. Ability to acquire information about related projects
3. Ability to trace the digital footprint of research outputs (publications, datasets and other related projects)
4. Ability to obtain information about the settings
5. Ability for metadata enrichment
6. Ability to complete missing information and links
7. Ability to demonstrate collaboration networks and subsequent impacts

Research Graph Augments API Capabilities

Research Graph augments Application Program Interface (API) capabilities by connecting PIDs such as ORCID, DOIs and so on, to establish linkages with research objects.

Table 3 represents the connections of PID ORCID with other types of PIDs such as DOIs and WikiData. By linking research objects with PIDs which enables connections across a global network of scholarly works, Research Graph is able to record the affiliations, publications, grants, datasets, etc. of independent researchers and/or organisations. For example, establishing a connection with ORCID will help record the publication history of the researcher (Table 3).

Table 3. Types of PID connections used by Research Graph for linking research objects

PID Connections
<i>Independent researchers/organisations</i>
ORCID → Publications.DOI
ORCID → Data.DOI
ORCID → Grant (DOI is coming soon)
ORCID → Organisation.Fundref
ORCID → Organisation.WikiData
<i>Multiple researchers/organisations</i>
ORCID → Publications.DOI → ORCID → Organisation.WikiData
ORCID → Data.DOI → ORCID → Organisation.WikiData
ORCID → Grant.ARC → ORCID → Organisation.WikiData

Risks and Challenges

1. Dataset DOIs may not be consistently possessed by all project partners
2. ORCID may not be possessed by all researchers and data consumers
3. All data and metadata are not made accessible to all – some records may be privatised and encrypted
4. Potential metadata challenges for exchanging metadata about sensitive projects
5. Legacy records may be connected to researchers who might not have ORCID
6. There is no adoption of organisation ID
7. Publication records may not have appropriate DOI and citation information in some cases
8. Grant records have no persistent identifiers till date

Project Partners

AAF – Australian Access Federation

AAF empowers Australian students, researchers, and educators by enabling seamless access through a single sign-on solution to online resources for the education and research communities. AAF also provides the underpinning access and authentication infrastructure for research in Australia.

AARNet – Australia’s Academic and Research Network

AARNet is purposed to deliver internet and layered services to the Australian education and research sectors and their research partners, and is the operator of the Advanced Research

and Education Network (AREN). AARNet provides underpinning national research e-Infrastructure.

ADA, ANU – Australian Data Archive, Australian National University

ADA provides a national service for the collection and preservation of digital research data and enables the dissemination of this data for secondary analysis by academic researchers and other users. ADA functions within the ANU Centre for Social Research and Methods based at the Australian National University.

AIFS – Australian Institute of Family Studies

AIFS advances understanding of the factors affecting Australian families through high-quality research and communicates those findings to policy makers, service providers and the broader community. AIFS operates within the portfolio of the Australian Government Department of Social Services.

AIHW – Australian Institute of Health and Welfare

AIHW is an independent statutory agency producing authoritative and accessible information and statistics to inform and support better policy and service delivery decisions, leading to better health and wellbeing for all Australians. AIHW focuses on turning data into useful information and narrating the broader story.

AURIN – Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network

AURIN is a provider of infrastructure and expert eResearch support for urban, regional and social science researchers across academia, government and industry sectors. AURIN offers access to high-quality, spatially enabled, national-scale data assets that cover climate, critical infrastructure, economics, health, housing, land use, planning, population, social policy and transport. By working with researchers, AURIN facilitates the development, deployment and long-term support of advanced analytical methods, simulation models, and visualisation capabilities for the adoption of high-impact research within government and industry across Australia.

ERICA, UNSW – E-Research Institutional Cloud Architecture, University of New South Wales

ERICA is a secure cloud computing infrastructure for researchers working with sensitive and often large-scale health data. ERICA is a network and nodes operate at UNSW Sydney, the AIHW (Secure Remote Analysis Environment – SRAE) and NSW Data Analytics Centre (NSW Secure Analytics Lab). New nodes are being added to the network that will operate in the University of Melbourne, SA-NT DataLink and the University of Western Australia.

ISSR, UQ – Institute for Social Science Research, The University of Queensland

ISSR conducts solution-focused to address new and emerging challenges facing Australian society and is an international leader in advanced interdisciplinary and evidence-based social science research. ISSR functions within the University of Queensland.

MGSE, UMELB – Melbourne Graduate School of Education, The University of Melbourne

MGSE supports people to address the major educational challenges of our times by fostering research and teaching that lead to the transformation of education practice and knowledge, both within and beyond the boundaries of the profession.

SoDA, SWIN - Social Data Analytics Lab, Swinburne University of Technology

SoDA is a research lab that applies contemporary and emerging co-operative data analytics techniques to provide insight into health and social problems. SoDA operates within the Social Innovation Research Institute at the Swinburne University of Technology and is a partner in the Data CO-OP.

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

CrossRef³

Crossref is an official digital object identifier Registration Agency of the International DOI Foundation. CrossRef makes scholarly communications better by making research objects easy to discover, track, cite, link, assess and reuse.

DOI – Digital Object Identifier

A DOI is a persistent interoperable identifier that uses a string of letters, numbers and symbols to permanently identify a research article or a document^{4,5}. A DOI attached to the citation helps people easily locate articles or documents on digital networks.

FundRef – CrossRef Funder Registry⁶

The CrossRef Funder Registry ensures transparency in research funding and its outcomes by providing funders with unique funder IDs. Funder Registry is an open and unique registry of persistent identifiers for grant-giving organizations worldwide.

GRID – Global Research Identifier Database⁷

GRID is a global and openly available database that catalogues research-related organisations and provides each with unique and persistent identifiers. GRID offers open organisation

³ <https://www.crossref.org/>

⁴ <https://www.doi.org/index.html>

⁵ <https://researchguides.uic.edu/doi>

⁶ <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

⁷ <https://www.grid.ac/>

identifiers that enables the quick identification and distinguishment of research-related institutions worldwide in the open research space.

ISBN – International Standard Book Number⁸

An ISBN is a product identifier that is unique to each book published, and it's every variation. The ISBN identifies the specific title, edition and format as well as the registrant (publisher, library, bookseller, etc.).

ORCID – Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier

An ORCID ID is a persistent digital identifier that can be owned and controlled, and that distinguishes researchers from one another. The ORCID ID can be connected with affiliations, grants, publications, and so on⁹.

ROR - Research Organization Registry¹⁰

ROR is a community-led registry of open, sustainable, usable, and unique identifiers for every research organization in the world. The ROR ID was developed for the research sector, for the purpose of increasing the use of organization identifiers for improving discovery and tracking of research outputs, and enabling connections between organization records across various platforms and systems.

⁸ <https://www.isbn-international.org/>

⁹ <https://orcid.org/>

¹⁰ <https://ror.org/>